

A Comparison of Science Between Similar GDP Countries: Spain, Mexico and Indonesia.

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Abstract—In this study is compared the state of science between countries with similar GDP, such as Spain, Mexico and Indonesia. For accomplish this goal, SciVal is used to achieve a quantitative collection of specific data on the production of scientific research in the field of informatics within these countries. In the investigation, factors such as the number of publications, the generation of impact in citations and the collaboration that institutions and authors can carry out were considered. The study proposes to distinguish between productivity and the footprint generated by scientific research in informatics by comparing these three countries, emphasizing the importance of factors that go beyond GDP to promote scientific innovation. This research is specially centered in computer science along this three countries.

Index Terms—Patent impact, Publications, Research areas, Performance indicators

I. INTRODUCTION

The gross domestic product (GDP) measures the monetary value of final goods and services—that is, those that are bought by the final user—produced in a country in a given period of time (say a quarter or a year). It counts all the output generated within the borders of a country. GDP is composed of goods and services produced for sale in the market and also includes some non-market production, such as defense or education services provided by the government. An alternative concept, gross national product, or GNP, counts all the output of the residents of a country. [1]

According to the International Monetary Fund, the GDP of Spain, Mexico and Indonesia are \$1,421,979, \$1,292,298 and \$1,183,053 millions of USD respectively; positioning them 14th, 15th and 16th place globally [5] [7] [8] [9]

The economic development of each country to be studied is linked to the investment that the government injects into research and development, mainly in the field of information technology. This injection of capital to this sector within the countries can generate a boost in technology and innovation, and in a dependent way this would generate economic growth within the country [6]. It is known that the gross domestic product is a very significant measure to evaluate the economic performance of any country, since it is the reflection of the goods and services generated within its

borders [2]. Consequently, countries with high GDP have greater capacities to generate capital injection in research and development sectors and thus be able to promote the field of information technology.

In the field of information technology, research and innovation have been very marked in recent years, since these innovations support a large number of technological advances that have driven modern society. This has been very marked with the introduction of artificial intelligence, the analysis of big data, the improvement of cybersecurity and innovation in software engineering, taking into account that information technology can have applications in most industrial sectors. Therefore, to generate greater innovation and competitiveness in the countries, it is suggested that they invest more in this research sector, since they will achieve greater technological progress [6].

This article compares the field of information technology between three countries with very similar GDPs: Spain, Mexico and Indonesia. The development of publications and the impact generated by each appointment in this sector of study within the three countries will be examined. The main objective of this study is to achieve the level of scientific productivity and innovation within our country and the countries that differ little in its GDP with respect to this

II. METHODOLOGY

In this paper, for every country compared, would be analyzed the scientific output on a time window of four years, the scientific impact through citations and other indicators on the same period and collaboration patterns of the country.

To generate the comparison of the state of scientific exploration in the area of information technology between Spain, Mexico and Indonesia, the SciVal tool is used, which works to analyze information that provides the performance of the investigations that have been carried out at different levels, such as, individual, institutional and national. The field of informatics was selected, since it is the study model in which the authors of this study are involved, as it is a rapidly

growing field with very significant impacts on innovation and the economic growth of a country.

Information was collected on the preparation of publications, the impact of citations and cooperation in informatics research with respect to each Country to be studied with the information provided by SciVal. The information studied covered the period 2017 to 2021. This period was chosen to ensure that our study was based on the most recent information available and to achieve an identification of propensities in a certain time.

A variety of measures were used in order to generate a complete study and thus achieve a concrete comparison in the results of scientific research for the area of informatics in the three countries, including the number of publications, the impact generated by citations of these publications and the level generated by international collaborations in studies. In the same way, the contributions of individual authors were evaluated, as well as the productivity and impact generated by the institutions within each country.

To achieve stable confidence and validation in the study, all SciVal information was cross-checked with other data sources such as Google Scholar and Web of Science. In the same way, a qualitative study of the findings of the information in the area of informatics was generated for each country, with the purpose of generating a correct understanding of the nature and qualities of the data that were generated.

To generalize, the methodology carried out helped us to achieve an exhaustive study of the state of scientific research in informatics for the three study countries and thus achieve a correct comparison between them, in order to find key similarities and differences that helped us to know more about economic and educational issues within each country and how these variables affect the productivity and impact of research within the field.

III. RESULTS

In this three countries, the area of computer science research is strongly influenced by academic institutions. These organisms are extremely important to achieve the promotion of innovation, collaboration and progress in research in specific areas such as information technology. In the same way, to contribute to the growth in the area of research at a national and international level, in order to achieve a training of specialist talents in specific topics. Below are examples of some of the main informatics research institutions in Spain, Mexico and Indonesia, as well as the most prominent informatics research areas in the three countries and International collaboration research in Spain, Mexico and Indonesia until 2021 [3].

A. Spain

The summary of this country (from 2017 to 2021) shows the following metrics:

- Number of publications indexed in Scopus - 546,261
- Authors - 401,745
- Citation Count - 7,379,162
- Citations per Publication - 13.5

The areas by subject area could be observed in the following figure. From here we can observe that medicine,

Fig. 1. Publication share by Subject Area - Spain

social sciences and engineering are the three biggest research areas.

B. International collaboration research in Spain

In order to understand collaboration in the different fields of research in Spain and how it affects scientific production and the impact of citations, the analysis of different types of research collaborations is introduced. These collaborations are classified as international collaboration, national collaboration, institutional collaboration, and single-authored works. As shown in table 1 below

Table 1. Spanish academic product, deferred in number of international, national and institutional collaborations

Metric	Percentage	Scholarly Output	Citations
International Collaboration	48.4%	265,051	5,261,149
National Collaborations	23.5%	128,580	1,334,587
Institutional Collaborations	18.5%	101,459	794,179
Single Outhship	9.6%	52,828	137,615

C. Leading informatics research institutions in Spain

Technical University of Madrid

- Total number of publications - 15,382
- Total number of citations - 194,149
- Citations per Publication - 12.6
- Computer Science publications - 4,282
- Computer Science citations - 38,894
- Computer Science authors - 2,991

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 2 how research is divided at the Technical University of Madrid. Being 27.8% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 2. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Technical University of Madrid

Polytechnic University of Catalonia

- Total number of publications - 19,105
- Total number of citations - 262,515
- Citations per Publication - 13.7
- Computer Science publications - 5,790
- Computer Science citations - 50,377
- Computer Science authors - 3,622

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 3 how research is divided at the Polytechnic University of Catalonia. Being 30.3% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 3. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Polytechnic University of Catalonia

University of Granada

- Total number of publications - 22,250
- Total number of citations - 323,779
- Citations per Publication - 14.6
- Computer Science publications - 2,965
- Computer Science citations - 49,152
- Computer Science authors - 1,948

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 4 how research is divided at the University of Granada. Being 13.3% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 4. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the University of Granada

D. Most prominent informatics research areas in Spain

In Spain, the area of informatics occupies 12% as a research area in the country, resulting in the following most popular subareas of informatics:

- Computer Network and Communication - 2.7%
- General Computer Science - 2.6%
- Software - 2.2%

E. Mexico

The summary of this country (from 2017 to 2021) shows the following metrics:

- Number of publications indexed in Scopus - 148,463
- Authors - 160,172
- Citation Count - 1,465,261
- Citations per Publication - 9.9

The areas by subject area could be observed in the following figure. From here we can observe that medicine,

Fig. 5. Publication share by Subject Area - Mexico

Agricultural and biological science and engineering are the three bigger research areas.

F. International collaboration research in Mexico

To understand the different fields of research in Mexico and how it affects the scientific sector, the analysis of the different types of research collaborations is introduced in table 2 below.

Table 2. Mexico academic product, deferred in number of international, national and institutional collaborations

Metric	Percentage	Scholarly Output	Citations
International Collaboration	41.8%	61,982	995,524
National Collaborations	28.4%	42,098	270,982
Institutional Collaborations	21.8%	32,312	170,774
Single Outhship	8.1%	12,071	27,981

G. Leading informatics research institutions in Mexico

Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

- Total number of publications - 36,168
- Total number of citations - 393,770
- Citations per Publication - 10.9
- Computer Science publications - 1,966
- Computer Science citations - 11,832
- Computer Science authors - 2,365

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 6 how research is divided at the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. Being 5.4% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 6. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

Instituto Politécnico Nacional

- Total number of publications - 13,901
- Total number of citations - 119,210
- Citations per Publication - 8.6
- Computer Science publications - 2,319
- Computer Science citations - 17,535
- Computer Science authors - 2,318

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 7 how research is divided at the Instituto Politécnico Nacional. Being 16.7% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 7. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Instituto Politécnico Nacional

Instituto Tecnológico de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey

- Total number of publications - 8,150
- Total number of citations - 99,788
- Citations per Publication - 12.2
- Computer Science publications - 1,766
- Computer Science citations - 14,898
- Computer Science authors - 1,419

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 8 how research is divided at the Instituto Tecnológico de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey. Being 21.7% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 8. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Instituto Tecnológico de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey

H. Most prominent informatics research areas in Mexico

In Mexico, the area of informatics occupies 11.6% as a research area in the country, resulting in the following most popular subareas of informatics:

- Computer Science Applications - 4.1%
- General Computer Science - 2.9%
- Artificial Intelligence - 2.3%

I. Indonesia

The summary of this country (from 2017 to 2021) shows the following metrics:

- Number of publications indexed in Scopus - 210,553
- Authors - 230,228
- Citation Count - 900,979
- Citations per Publication - 4.3

The areas by subject area could be observed in the following figure. From here we can observe that physics and

Fig. 9. Publication share by Subject Area - Indonesia

astronomy, Environmental sciences and engineering are the three bigger research areas.

J. International collaboration research in Indonesia

To understand the different fields of research in Indonesia and how it affects the scientific sector, the analysis of the different types of research collaborations is introduced in table 3 below.

Table 3. Indonesia academic product, deferred in number of international, national and institutional collaborations

Metric	Percentage	Scholarly Output	Citations
International Collaboration	17.9%	37,763	433,482
National Collaborations	21.2%	44,690	147,005
Institutional Collaborations	55.2%	116,270	292,481
Single Outhship	5.6%	11,830	28,011

K. Leading informatics research institutions in Indonesia

University of Indonesia

- Total number of publications - 20,190
- Total number of citations - 108,935
- Citations per Publication - 5.4
- Computer Science publications - 3,253
- Computer Science citations - 10,887
- Computer Science authors - 3,484

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 10 how research is divided at the University of Indonesia. Being 16.1% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 10. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the University of Indonesia

Gadjah Mada University

- Total number of publications - 12,173
- Total number of citations - 56,897
- Citations per Publication - 4.7
- Computer Science publications - 1,773
- Computer Science citations - 7,634
- Computer Science authors - 1,761

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 11 how research is divided at the Gadjah Mada University. Being 14.6% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 11. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Gadjah Mada University

Bandung Institute of Technology

- Total number of publications - 11,234
- Total number of citations - 54,024

- Citations per Publication - 4.8
- Computer Science publications - 3,147
- Computer Science citations - 10,729
- Computer Science authors - 3,146

In the area of computing, it can be seen in Figure 12 how research is divided at the Bandung Institute of Technology. Being 28% the computer science representation of the research areas within this university

Fig. 12. Publications shared by the area of computer science by the Bandung Institute of Technology

L. Most prominent informatics research areas in Indonesia

In Indonesia, the area of informatics occupies 16.5% as a research area in the country, resulting in the following most popular subareas of informatics:

- Computer Network and Communication - 7.5%
- Computer Science Applications - 6.1%
- Information System - 5.1%

IV. DISCUSSION

The state of science between Spain, Mexico and Indonesia has not a correlation with GDP from each country. From the three nations, Spain is the one with a greater GDP and so it has the bigger scientific performance (based on number of publications); but the same isn't true for Mexico and Indonesia, the former has a bigger GDP than the latter, but Indonesia has a greater scientific performance than Mexico. The only two parameters measured in the study that seems to have a correlation with GDP are number of citations and citations per publications, as the country with more citations is Spain, followed by Mexico and finally by Indonesia.

Between these three countries, the academic production is more similar between Spain and Mexico, about having the majority of its production by international collaborations, unlike Indonesia, that its mayor production is based on institutional collaboration.

From the most prominent institutions of each country, the one with a bigger number of publications is Technical university of Madrid. And the one with a bigger percentage of the total investigation in computational science is Bandung Institute of Technology.

V. CONCLUSION

This article examined the scientific output and collaboration patterns in the fields of chemistry and physics for three different countries: Spain, Mexico, and Indonesia. While Spain has the highest GDP among the three countries and therefore the highest scientific output in terms of publication numbers, it is interesting to note that Mexico and Indonesia have comparable publication numbers, despite the latter having a smaller GDP. This suggests that there are factors beyond GDP that influence a country's scientific output.

One such factor is the international collaboration pattern, as both Spain and Mexico have a significant portion of their publications resulting from international collaborations, whereas Indonesia's research tends to be more domestically-focused. Additionally, the study found that the citation performance is correlated with the GDP, as Spain has the highest number of citations, followed by Mexico and Indonesia. This indicates that despite similar publication numbers, the quality and impact of research may vary between these countries.

Furthermore, the study identified the most productive institutions in each country, with the Technical University of Madrid having the most publications among the three countries, and the Bandung Institute of Technology having the highest percentage of publications in the field of computational science.

Future research in this area can expand on this study by including more countries and research fields, as well as examining additional factors that may influence a country's scientific output. This could include factors such as government investment in research, educational policies, and infrastructure development. Additionally, further research could explore the impact of international collaborations on the quality and impact of research. Overall, this study provides insights into the scientific output and collaboration patterns of these three countries, and lays the groundwork for future research in this area.

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